

Digital Innovation Hub Networks

The DIHNET.EU project enables the coordination of European, national and regional initiatives directly supporting the digital transformation and Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs). The project aims to create a sustainable pan-European network of networks, with a focus on regional DIHs.

The DIHNET.EU project supports these networks and initiatives by establishing a coordination mechanism, creating synergies and addressing common issues.

More specifically, it contributes to:

- Enhance the collaboration between the different stakeholders from the European DIH Community with a wide range of services, information and tools that will help DIHs to communicate, align, collaborate and synchronize activities.
- Develop a clear overview of the DIHs related services provided in Europe and align them.
- Upgrade the DIH Catalogue by identifying/triggering activities in the DIH Community in coherence with regional, national and EU policies.
- Create a strategy to reinforce the specialisation of these services, as well as supporting its uptake by relevant DIHs and DIH networks.
- Create a vision and strategy on a self-sustaining business model for this network of DIHs, and to make this operational.
- Create an online community to foster interaction among hubs, information exchange and peer-learning.

Business models to create sustainable collaboration

European collaboration between technology oriented and local DIHs will develop and bring full growth potential if all stakeholders take benefits and generate value from it. In this respect, the efficiency of business models generating a specific European added-value out of this pan-European collaboration is key.

The objective is to identify, develop and promote the diversity of new business models that foster knowledge sharing and technologies transfer between European DIHs while enabling the sustainable development of new business opportunities for them all.

DIHNET.EU reinforces smart specialization by stimulating cross-fertilization between technology oriented and sectorial DIHs.

DIHs and Specialisation

Collaboration among Competence Centres, Digital Innovation Hubs, regional and European Initiatives is crucial in order to offer the best possible support for SMEs and Midcaps.

The DIHNET.EU project will support stakeholders in developing specialisation strategies that will help their clients and partners to develop a portfolio of services based on regional assets and comparative advantages.

DIH concept and evolution

The concepts and practice of DIHs and networks of hubs have evolved from the Competence Centres, being the core mechanisms to support digitisation, to the creation of structures where different public and private stakeholders work together to support SMEs as a Digital Innovation Hub.

Also, the growth of Regional DIHs networks working as a cross sectoral and multi-technology one-stop-shop for SMEs, supported at the same time at National and European level, show the need of moving towards a pan-European network of DIHs where DIHs offer the best possible support for SMEs and midcaps everywhere in Europe regardless of the technological domain and removing any constraints linked to regional capacities.

Within this framework, DIHNET.EU will facilitate the creation of a pan-European network of DIHs to foster the cooperation between regions offering tools to move from the traditional regional approach, to a network of DIHs acting as a doorway of European capacities to boost SMEs competitiveness.

Catalogue of DIHs

The European catalogue of DIHs, created by the Joint Research Centre (JRC), is an online repository which contains comprehensive information on digital innovation hubs across Europe. This tool aims at helping companies get access to competences needed in order to digitize their products and services.

DIHNET.EU will contribute to upgrade and update the information included in the catalogue of DIHs.

Contact

Scientific Manager

Maurits Butter
maurits.butter@tno.nl
+31610939947
Anna van Buerenplein 1
2595 DA Den Haag
The Netherlands

Project Manager

Ruud Baartmans
ruud.baartmans@tno.nl
+31646847439
Anna van Buerenplein 1
2595 DA Den Haag
The Netherlands

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